

EXPERIMENTAL OPTIMIZATION OF ORBITAL DRILLING OF WOVEN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Defects associated with drilling of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) are of major economic and safety concerns for aerospace manufacturers. One of the most critical defects associated with the drilling of CFRP laminates is the delamination of layers, which can be avoided by keeping the drilling forces below some threshold levels [1].

Conventional drilling of CFRP has been extensively studied to investigate the effect of tool geometry [2-6] and cutting parameters [7-10] on the hole quality, especially, delamination, thermal damage, and surface roughness. Rawat and Attia [11, 12] studied the effect of feeds and speeds on the quality of drilled holes using machinability maps. The different mechanisms for the tool wear were considered. The three dominant wear mechanisms were found to be fracture (chipping) at the start of drilling process, followed by subsequent abrasion and adhesion of carbon to the tool. Hocheng and Tsao [2, 3] developed a linear fracture mechanics model for conventional drilling to predict the threshold level of axial forces for the onset of exit delamination of CFRP, for different tool geometries. This model is based on the balance of the work done by the axial drilling force, the strain energy of the last ply at the hole exit, and the energy required to form a new surface by fracture.

Orbital Drilling (OD) is an emerging drilling process that exhibits lower cutting forces and temperatures, easier chip removal, higher produced surface quality, longer tool life and a high possibility for dry machining. In OD, the cutting tool rotates about its own axis and simultaneously about the axis of the desired cylindrical hole at an eccentric distance as it is fed along the hole depth following a helical path, as shown in Fig. 1. The OD process is featured by cyclic engagement and disengagement between the

tool and the work-piece [13-16]. The research work published in [14] explained the reduction in the cutting temperature and the risk of exit delamination in OD from an energy perspective. The reduction in the OD axial forces is attributed to the helical motion of the tool in which a considerable part of the work done by the tool is directed towards the tangential direction while the work done in the axial direction is reduced. This reduces the risk of delamination at the exit. Moreover, in OD the tool applies a distributed load on the laminate in the axial direction which results in less ply deflection compared to the concentrated loading in the case of conventional drilling using a point-drill. It was also demonstrated that enhanced cooling is achieved due to the formation of vortices in an unstable air flow regime in the annular gap [14].

Part of the research work available on OD was performed by industrial organizations [17, 18] that are more interested in the technology rather than the mechanics of the process. This research work represents a unique experimental study on the OD technique of woven CFRP laminates.

The research work published in [15] showed the results of using OD to produce holes in sandwich constructions of CFRPs with aluminum honeycomb core and for aerospace applications. This process produced delamination-free holes with allowable geometric accuracy. The tool experienced, however, considerable chipping on the main cutting edge, due to the lack of tool dynamic stability. Brinksmeier et al. [19] compared the effect of conventional drilling and OD processes on the quality of the holes produced in sandwich materials of Al-CFRP-Ti. It could be proven through this study that OD was associated with lower cutting forces and temperatures compared to conventional drilling. On the other hand, the high rotational speeds resulted in lower hole surface quality for the CFRP layer.

However, the effect of the main OD process parameters applied to CFRPs is not fully understood so far, whereas such understanding is essential for process optimization and design. The objective of this research work is to investigate the effect of the OD process key parameters with respect to their corresponding produced hole quality attributes and cutting forces and temperatures. This study illustrates the capabilities and limitations of the OD process and opening the door for the OD process design and optimization.

2 Experimental Setup

All the OD tests were performed under dry conditions on a 5-axis Makino A88ε machining center. Fig. 2 shows the experimental set-up used for the drilling experiments. Fixture (1) was used to hold the CFRP laminates. The fine chips were evacuated using a special vacuum arrangement (2). The cutting forces were recorded using a 3-component dynamometer (3), Kistler 9255B, and 5070A Kistler charge amplifier. Cutting temperatures were measured using a FLIR ThermoVision A20M Infrared camera (4) at the hole exits. The large compartment required to accommodate the IR camera to monitor the temperature at the exit of the hole places the cutting zone at a position beyond the recommended measuring distance from the dynamometer face, which might significantly affect the accuracy of the measured forces. The use of a special reflection mirror to reflect the emitted IR rays towards the lens of the IR camera, as shown in Fig. 3, requires a smaller compartment compared to that required for placing the IR camera.

The test material used was a quasi-isotropic laminate comprising 35 plies of 8-harness satin woven graphite epoxy prepreg. The laminate was manufactured by autoclave molding with a cure time of 60 min at 127 °C under 516.75 kPa autoclave pressure to produce a final cured thickness of 6.35 ± 0.02 mm. The OD tests were performed using a four flute 6.35 mm end-mill with a fluted length of 19 mm and a total length of 63 mm.

Delamination at the entry and exit of holes were investigated using the Olympus Model GZX 12 optical microscope. Hole circularity and hole size errors along the depth of the hole were measured using a “Mitutoyo-Mach 806” coordinate

measuring machine (CMM). Surface roughness measurements were done using a Form Talysurf series 2 surface profilometer.

Tables

Table 1 shows the ranges of axial feeds corresponding to the two levels of helical pitches used (1 mm and 3 mm) with spindle speeds of 6000, 8000, 10000, 120000 and 16000 rpm. The orbital speeds used were 60, 80, 100, and 120 rpm. For the purpose of comparison, a 9.5 mm hole diameter was produced by conventional drilling, using a 3 flute twist drill, and by OD using a 4 flute end mill, for the same rotational speed and axial feed; $n=6000$ rpm, and $f=360$ mm/min.

3 Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of the forces and temperatures are discussed and related to the hole quality parameters, including the hole entry and exit delamination, surface roughness, as well as hole size, circularity, and concentricity errors.

3.1 Axial and tangential cutting forces

In machining processes, most of the material and tool damage could be explained through investigating the drilling forces generated during the machining process. The OD drilling force signal in OD comprises features from the drilling and milling force signals. Fig. 4 shows an axial force signal for OD of woven CFRP laminate. The axial force (F_z) steeply increases from a value of zero to its maximum value when the flute cutting edges of the tool have engaged into the workpiece material to a depth equal to the pitch length. The axial force then starts to fluctuate as the tool performs a helical path towards the exit of the hole. This fluctuation is a collective resultant of the orbital motion (lower frequency fluctuation of the mean force value), the intermittent cutting of the up-milling regime as the tool rotates about its axis, and the anisotropy of the woven CFRP laminate being cut (responsible for the high frequency force fluctuation around the mean value). The axial force (F_z) starts decreasing when the end of the tool breaks through the hole exit, and keeps decreasing until it reaches a value of zero when the hole is completely produced.

Fig. 5 shows the in-plane horizontal force (F_x) and vertical force (F_y) signals for OD of woven CFRP laminate. Both force components possess similar signal forms with a phase shift near $(\pi/2)$ between the signals of both force components. Through the helical path, the horizontal force (F_x) reaches its maximum mean value as the tangential cutting speed vector becomes aligned with the “x-axis” and as the tool engages with the uncut material normal to the cutting velocity vector; a position shown in Fig.6a. This also marks the point at which the mean value of the vertical force (F_y) component is equal to zero. The horizontal force (F_x) reaches a mean value of zero at the position shown in Fig.6b, where the maximum mean value of the vertical force (F_y) takes place. The in-plane forces fluctuate around a mean of zero. The dynamometer records an extreme positive and negative value of each of the in-plane force components per cycle following the alignment of the cutting vector directions with the coordinates of the dynamometer.

The influences of spindle speed and helical feed on the average axial forces for 1 mm and 3 mm helical pitches are shown in Fig. 7. An average increase of nearly 90% in the average axial force can be seen as a result of higher (3 mm) pitch compared to the lower (1 mm) pitch. This increase in force is expected due to the larger uncut chip area in the case of the higher pitch. For both (1 mm and 3 mm) pitches, it can be observed that the average axial force increased as the helical feed increased. This direct relationship is due to the higher material removal rate (MRR) resulting from the higher helical feed, which requires higher force to perform cutting as the tool advances. On the other hand, the chip load reduction associated with increasing the spindle speed led to reducing the average axial force in an inverse relationship with the spindle speed.

The average resultant in-plane forces (F_r) for all OD conditions are compared in Fig. 8. “ F_r ” represents the mean value of the resultant horizontal force (F_x) and vertical forces (F_y) calculated for the tool position at an angle 45 degrees, as shown in Fig.6. The 3 mm pitch generated in-plane forces around 50% higher than the 1 mm pitch. This increase is attributed to the higher material removal rate (MRR) in the case of the 3 mm pitch. In Fig. 8, a positive relationship can be observed between the helical feed and the measured resultant in-plane force, except for the 8000 rpm condition with the 3 mm

pitch. On the other hand, the relationship between the spindle speed and the measured resultant in-plane force does not follow a fixed trend. Analysis of the results showed 45% reduction in the axial force component in orbital drilling (OD), compared to conventional drilling. This can be explained in relation to the redistribution of the cutting energy in OD.

3.2 Hole entry and exit delamination

The hole entry and exit delamination were investigated. None of the holes produced by the entire set of experiments has experienced a considerable entry or exit delamination. Fig. 9 (a) and (b) show the delamination-free exit edges of the holes that experienced the highest axial forces at a speed of 6000 rpm and pitch (a) 1 mm and (b) 3 mm. The delamination-free hole exits suggest that the level of the drilling axial force in all the OD conditions did not exceed the critical axial threshold value.

This is explained by the fact that in conventional drilling, the zero tangential velocity drilling tool center dwells over the uncut material thickness throughout the drilling process creating interlaminar delamination if it exceeds the critical axial force limit [2]. For OD, the helical tool motion during hole making eliminates the tool center dwelling over the uncut material thickness hence reducing chances of interlaminar delamination either at the hole entry or exit.

3.3 Temperature

Thermal damage during machining is a critical aspect that must be considered while studying the impact of different process parameters on hole quality attributes. CFRPs are sensitive to thermal damage that causes material deterioration by decomposition at the machined surface and/or within the heat affected zones. Fig. 10 shows the effect of rotational speed and helical feed and pitch on the OD maximum recorded temperatures. The temperatures were measured at the exit of the hole immediately before the tool exit. The results show an average of 20% increase in the OD temperature in the case of 3 mm pitch compared to 1 mm pitch. This is attributed to the higher frictional force generated as a result of larger engagement length on the cutting tool in the case of higher pitch. For the conventional drilling, at an axial feed of 360 m/min and a speed of 6,000 rpm, the temperature is 255°C

which is almost double that of the OD process at the same cutting conditions. This confirms the suggested mechanism of cooling presented in [14] due to the presence of Taylor vortices in annular gaps.

3.4 Hole surface quality

The arithmetical mean surface roughness 'Ra' was measured along the hole depth in order to represent the quality of the produced hole surface. Fig. 11 shows a map for the surface roughness of the holes produced by OD. For rotational speeds 6,000 rpm to 10,000 rpm, the surface roughness was found to be less sensitive to the effect of axial feed. For higher rotational speeds (12,000 rpm and 16,000 rpm), the surface roughness experienced a dramatic increase especially with higher axial feeds. This could be attributed to the fiber pull-out at higher rotational speeds as well as the growing effect of tool dynamics that results in poor fiber cutting. For the conventional drilling, the surface roughness is 1.83 μm .

3.5 Hole size accuracy

The hole size error is defined by the ratio of the difference between the actual hole diameter " D_a ", and the nominal hole diameter " D_n " to the nominal hole diameter (Hole Size Error (%) = $(D_a - D_n)/D_n \times 100$). A negative error indicates that the produced hole is smaller than the nominal size. The limits of allowable tolerance on most of the drilling tools range between ($\pm 0.12\%$ and $\pm 0.15\%$). The accuracy of the hole size in the case of OD depends on the precision of the helical path generated by the machine tool at the first place.

Fig. 12 shows the percentage of hole size errors for holes produced at 1mm and 3mm pitches, respectively. The tool dynamics effect resulting in oversized holes due to possible tool whirling at high speeds, and the tool deflection towards the hole center under the action of the radial force components are two factors that control the accuracy of holes produced by OD. The low pitch (1 mm) OD produced undersized hole sizes within acceptable tolerance limits, except the low speed conditions which produced out-of-tolerance under sized holes. The negative error of the hole size increased with the increase in feed, as a result of the growing effect of tool deflection with higher forces associated with high feeds. On the other hand, the negative error of the hole size decreased with the increase in

rotational speed, as a result of the tool dynamics effect rectifying the effect of tool deflection.

The high pitch (3 mm) OD with low rotational speeds (6,000 rpm and 8,000 rpm) produced under-sized hole sizes beyond acceptable tolerance limits. This is attributed to the dominating tool deflection effect with high pitch combined with low tool dynamics effect at low rotational speeds. Holes produced at 10,000 rpm exhibited an inflection from a positive to a negative error at the range of low feed. At high rotational speeds (12,000 rpm and 16,000 rpm), the significant effect of tool dynamics resulted in out of tolerance oversized holes (positive error) that decreased as the feed increased due to the growing effect of tool deflection. As compared to the conventional drilling, the hole size errors in OD are relatively higher due to the smaller size of the tool and the higher tangential forces. For the conventional drilling, at a speed of 6,000 rpm and a feed of 360 mm/min, the error is 0.03%.

The hole circularity errors are shown in Fig. 13. The circularity errors for the higher pitch (3 mm) are three times higher than for the lower pitch (1 mm). This is mainly attributed to the increased in-plane forces for the higher pitch. The effect of speed is more pronounced for the higher pitch where the circularity increased with increase in speed.

The hole concentricity errors are shown in Fig. 14. In general, the error levels for the concentricity and circularity are below the industrial requirements which often are set to 25 μm . No definite trend is seen for all the conditions. At low orbital pitch (1 mm), one can notice that for a given feed, the concentricity tends to increase with speed, but at the highest speed (16,000 rpm), there is a considerable reduction in error.

Conclusions

The effect of the cutting parameters (feed and speed) in the orbital drilling process on the cutting forces, temperatures, and hole quality attributes was presented. It was shown that the thrust forces increase with axial feed and decrease with the speed, while the temperature increases with both speed and feed. Delamination-free hole were obtained with orbital drilling. The hole size error was governed by the two competing factors, namely, the deflection due to the cutting forces and the tool dynamics due

to the higher rotational speeds. It was found that the orbital drilling offered reduced thrust forces, lower temperatures, and better surface roughness than conventional drilling. The in-plane forces and the hole size errors were higher than conventional drilling. Machinability maps were presented to serve as a tool for the optimization of the cutting parameters within the quality requirements constraints.

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References

- [1] Ho-Cheng, H., and Dharan, C. K. H., 1990, "Delamination During Drilling in Composite Laminates," *Journal of Engineering for Industry*, 112(3).
- [2] Hocheng, H., and Tsao, C. C., 2003, "Comprehensive analysis of delamination in drilling of composite materials with various drill bits," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 140(1-3), pp. 335-339.
- [3] Hocheng, H., and Tsao, C. C., 2006, "Effects of special drill bits on drilling-induced delamination of composite materials," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 46(12-13), pp. 1403-1416.
- [4] Abrão, A. M., Rubio, J. C. C., Faria, P. E., and Davim, J. P., 2008, "The effect of cutting tool geometry on thrust force and delamination when drilling glass fibre reinforced plastic composite," *Materials & Design*, 29(2), pp. 508-513.
- [5] Marques, A. T., Durão, L. M., Magalhães, A. G., Silva, J. F., and Tavares, J. M. R. S., 2009, "Delamination analysis of carbon fibre reinforced laminates: Evaluation of a special step drill," *Composites Science and Technology*, 69(14), pp. 2376-2382.
- [6] Shyha, I. S., Aspinwall, D. K., Soo, S. L., and Bradley, S., 2009, "Drill geometry and operating effects when cutting small diameter holes in CFRP," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 49(12-13), pp. 1008-1014.
- [7] Tagliaferri, V., Caprino, G., and Diterlizzi, A., 1990, "Effect of drilling parameters on the finish and mechanical properties of GFRP composites," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 30(1), pp. 77-84.
- [8] Mohan, N. S., Kulkarni, S. M., and Ramachandra, A., 2007, "Delamination analysis in drilling process of glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) composite materials," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 186(1-3), pp. 265-271.
- [9] Tsao, C. C., 2008, "Investigation into the effects of drilling parameters on delamination by various step-core drills," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 206(1-3), pp. 405-411.
- [10] Tsao, C. C., 2008, "Experimental study of drilling composite materials with step-core drill," *Materials & Design*, 29(9), pp. 1740-1744.
- [11] Rawat, S., and Attia, H., 2009, "Characterization of the dry high speed drilling process of woven composites using Machinability Maps approach," *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 58(1), pp. 105-108.
- [12] Rawat, S., and Attia, H., 2009, "Wear mechanisms and tool life management of WC-Co drills during dry high speed drilling of woven carbon fibre composites," *Wear*, 267(5-8), pp. 1022-1030.
- [13] Sadek, A., Meshreki, M., Zhongde, S., and Attia, H., 2010, "A Comparative Study on Conventional and Orbital Drilling of Woven Carbon Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Laminates," 2nd International Conference, Process Machine Interactions Vancouver.
- [14] Sadek, A., Meshreki, M., and Attia, M. H., 2012, "Characterization and optimization of orbital drilling of woven carbon fiber reinforced epoxy laminates," *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 61(1), pp. 123-126.
- [15] Lindqvist, R., Eriksson, I., and Wolf, M., 2001, "Orbital Drilling of Sandwich Constructions for Space Applications," 2001 Automated Fastening Conference & Exposition Seattle, Washington, United States
- [16] Iyer, R., Koshy, P., and Ng, E., 2007, "Helical milling: An enabling technology for hard machining precision holes in AISI D2 tool steel," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 47(2), pp. 205-210.

[17] Persson, E., Eriksson, I., and Zackrisson, L., 1997, "Effects of hole machining defects on strength and fatigue life of composite laminates," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 28(2), pp. 141-151.

[18] Persson, E., Eriksson, I., and Hammersberg, P., 1997, "Propagation of hole machining defects in pin-loaded composite laminates," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31(4), pp. 383-408.

[19] Brinksmeier, E., Fangmann, S., and Rentsch, R., 2011, "Drilling of composites and resulting surface integrity," *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 60(1), pp. 57-60.

Tables

Table 1: Axial feeds of orbital drilling

Helical pitch	Axial feeds (mm/min)			
1mm	60	80	100	120
3mm	180	240	300	360

Figures

Fig. 1: Description of tool and motion in orbital drilling

Fig. 2: (a) OD experimental setup, (b) setup for infrared (IR) temperature measurement at the hole exit

Fig. 3. Schematic of the IR temperature measurement setup

Fig. 4 Axial force signal for OD of woven CFRP laminate (feed = 1200mm/min, speed = 6000rpm and 1mm pitch)

Fig. 5 Horizontal and vertical (in-plane) force signals for OD of woven CFRP laminate (feed=1200mm/min, speed = 6000 rpm and 1mm pitch)

Fig. 6. In-plane (horizontal and vertical) force components at different tool positions

Fig. 7. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on axial force

Fig. 8. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on cutting force

Fig. 9. Hole exit for axial feeds (a) 120 mm/min and (b) 360 mm/min

Fig. 10. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on cutting temperature

Fig. 11. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on surface roughness of holes

Fig. 12. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on hole size errors

Fig. 13: Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on circularity errors

Fig. 14. Effect of OD axial feed and rotational speed on concentricity errors